

Covalent Organic Framework-Derived Highly Defective Carbon-Integrated Polymer Composite Electrode for Supercapacitor Applications

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Abstract

Heteroatoms-doped porous carbons are attractive electrode materials for supercapacitors due to their high specific capacitance and desirable surface properties. Here, we report a porous carbon (PI-COF-700) derived from covalent organic framework (COF) that is rich in nitrogen species with an appreciable yield. The polyimide COF (PI-COF) was synthesized through the condensation reaction of 1,3,5-tris(4-aminophenyl) benzene (TAPB) and pyromellitic dianhydride (PMDA) under solvothermal conditions. The amorphous defective carbon nature and variation in functional groups of pyrolyzed PI-COF-700 were studied through physicochemical characterizations. In addition, the porous carbon presents a large surface area of $1080 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ and high micropore distribution ratio, which was observed from nitrogen adsorption/desorption isotherm measurement. Later, we developed a strategy of compositing PI-COF-700 with polyaniline (PANI) and Poly (3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene: poly (4-styrene sulfonate) (PEDOT: PSS) as an electrode material for supercapacitor application. The modified composite material exhibited high specific capacitance value of 729.17 Fg^{-1} at an applied current density of 2 Ag^{-1} , surpassing many of previously reported supercapacitors based on organic framework derived porous carbon composite systems. In addition, the PANI/PEDOT: PSS@PI-COF-700 showed a capacitance retention close to $\sim 92.2\%$ after 1000 cycles at an applied current density of 20 Ag^{-1} . An aqueous electrolyte based symmetric supercapacitor electrode system constructed with this material demonstrated a specific capacitance of $\sim 182 \text{ Fg}^{-1}$ at 0.2 Ag^{-1} and 89.81% retention after 10,000 cycles at 30 Ag^{-1} .

Keywords

COF pyrolysis, Defective carbon, Porous material, Polymer composite, Symmetric supercapacitors.

Introduction

Smart, hybrid energy storage devices suited for wearable technologies, robotics, and high-performance applications have attracted significant interest in recent years [1]. Particularly, supercapacitors (SCs) are vital energy storage device that has drawn significant attention in industrial application due to their high-power density and long cycling life. They offer higher energy density than traditional capacitors, bridging the gap between capacitors and batteries. SCs are favoured over batteries because of their quick charging and stable discharging characteristics. However, the energy density of present SCs is insufficient than that of batteries (150 Wh/kg) and is not enough to meet the industrial demands [2]. However, the design of electrode materials with high capacitance, long-term stability, and stable charge-discharge rates is crucial [3]. To begin with the charge storage mechanism, SC's can be divided into electrochemical double layer capacitors (EDLCs - a non-faradaic type), in which charge is stored by physical adsorption of ions on the surface, and pseudocapacitors (faradaic type), in which charge accumulation occurs by the redox reactions near the surface [3,4]. The EDLC mechanism is generally found in carbon-based materials, while conducting polymers, metals, and metal oxide systems falls under pseudocapacitive behaviour [3]. In order to improve the capacitance property, several nanocomposites that combines EDLC and pseudocapitance performances have been previously studied [4]. While considering about electrode materials, Carbon is the backbone of SCs, whether if it is used as an active material in EDLC supercapacitors or as an additive in binary or ternary composite in pseudocapacitors [5,6]. Therefore, many advanced supercapacitors have utilised carbonaceous materials as active electrode with different physicochemical properties, such as carbon nanotubes (CNTs), carbon aerogels, graphite, activated carbon (AC) and templated porous carbon [5,6]. Owing to the exceptional merits of large surface area, inexpensive cost, low toxic nature and easy accessibility, AC are often preferred as one of the most popular commercial electrode materials for SC application [7,8]. Nevertheless, AC based supercapacitors have high power density ($>10 \text{ kW kg}^{-1}$), low energy density ($<20 \text{ Wh kg}^{-1}$) in comparison to lithium-ion batteries ($>250 \text{ Wh kg}^{-1}$). This observation is thought to be a key obstacle to their continued usage in large-scale energy storage system [9,10]. On the other hand, graphene, characterized by sp^2 hybridized atoms, has an excellent mechanical strength, robust chemical stability, high electrical & thermal conductivity, and a large surface area ($2630 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$) [11]. These properties render graphene as an attractive material for electrochemical energy storage applications. Despite these extraordinary physical properties, graphene undergoes irreversible re-stacking and aggregation during the

charging and discharging cycle, which degrades the overall electrochemical performance [12]. To address these problems, the use of porous carbonaceous materials with tunable pore structure and surface morphology has been observed as the most effective approach. In particular, well-developed porous carbon with dimensionally (1, 2, 3D) interconnected pores are more attractive because: 1) Interconnected voids can maximize the active site for chemical reactions and enhance electrolyte transport [13]. 2) Ordered nanostructures have improved electrical performance and continue to have better mechanical stability during cycling process [14]. 3) High capacitance guest materials (such as conducting polymers, metal oxides) can be uniformly distributed throughout the pores of the carbon structure when employed as a host material in composite systems [15, 16].

Furthermore, it has been demonstrated that doping of porous network with defects/heteroatom (B, N, O, P etc) significantly enhanced the charge storage mechanism by improving the interlayer structure and changing the surface chemistry of porous carbon electrodes [17,18]. Standard methods for preparing porous carbon include activation, chemical vapor deposition, template approach, and pyrolysis. However, during KOH activation, a significant amount of material is lost due to the strong corrosive nature of KOH, resulting in lower yields and higher costs [19, 20]. Among various methods, pyrolysis is a common and simple method for producing carbonaceous materials from various precursors such as biomass, organic frameworks, and other organic systems at above 500 °C in an inert atmosphere. Biomass-derived carbon materials have been widely used in supercapacitor electrodes due to the advantages of large surface area (870-2900 m²/g), excellent conductivity, light weight and cost effectiveness [21]. However, biomass-derived porous carbon often has a heterogeneous surface due to the diverse chemical composition nature and irregular porosity of the starting materials, which leads to inconsistent performance in selective adsorption and catalytic processes [22]. This complex porosity nature of biomass-derived porous carbon reduces its efficiency in applications like gas storage and supercapacitors, which require a large surface area and uniform pores. In some cases, biomass-derived porous carbon often requires further activation to achieve higher surface properties [22]. Therefore, the selection of noble heteroatom-doping with a rigid porous structure for pyrolysis synthesis is advantageous over other materials with random surface properties.

In recent years, covalent organic frameworks (COFs) have gained much interest in utilizing them as precursors for porous carbon preparation [23, 24, 25]. Typically, COFs possess a high specific surface area, conjugated moieties, and customizable heteroatom doping (such as

nitrogen, sulfur, hydrogen and boron in extended 2D or 3D structures). They own an organized porous network with a periodic skeleton that is lightweight and mechanically rigid network. They possess wide variety of applications such as gas storage, semiconductor, photoconductive devices energy storage and heterogeneous catalysis. These ordered porous organic frameworks are advantageous as potential electrode materials due to their robust networks, and open pores that allow more electrolyte ion transport [26]. Despite this excellent structural property, they suffer from limited conductivity. Currently, there is a growing interest in the pyrolysis of COF for porous carbon synthesis [23, 24]. Especially the designed heteroatoms on the COF surface can be inherited into the porous carbon for the efficient capacitance behaviour, and the conjugated network ensures the possibility of having high conductivity in the resulting carbon material [27]. Numerous porous carbons derived from metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) have also been studied in the past; however, since the MOF-derived porous carbons may not be fully carbonized, they often suffer from metal contamination [28, 29].

In 2016, Feng et al. prepared a porous carbon (surface area-880 m^2g^{-1}) by pyrolyzing a fully conjugated sp^2 -COF at 800 $^\circ\text{C}$, which exhibited a high capacitance of 334 Fg^{-1} at 0.5 Ag^{-1} with stable cycling stability compared to other porous carbon materials pyrolyzed at different temperatures [23]. Later in 2017, Xu et al. prepared an imine COF-coated (polycyclotriphosphazene-co-4,4'-sulfonyldiphenol) sphere, which is pyrolyzed at 900 $^\circ\text{C}$, and the resulting TAPT-DHTA-COF_{0.1}-PPZS₉₀₀ (surface area-456 m^2g^{-1}) composite exhibited a specific capacitance of 184 Fg^{-1} at a current density of 10 Ag^{-1} with stable cycling efficiency [24]. In 2023, N-doped carbon nanosheets (surface area - 672.2 m^2g^{-1}) were prepared from triazine-containing polyimide COF pyrolyzed at 700 $^\circ\text{C}$, which has been reported as an efficient electrocatalyst for hydrogen evolution [25]. Among many COF precursors, aromatic polyimides (PI) are unique materials for carbonization, which have attracted much attention in the research field due to their convenient processability, efficient graphitization and high carbon yield [27, 30, 31]. Especially, in laser-induced carbonization, PI substrates are mainly used due to the strong influence of the rigid structure on the resulting carbon skeleton (Kapton) [31]. However, due to the incredibly fast processing of the laser induction method, the carbon purity is much lower or insufficient in this procedure [31, 32]. Taking advantage of well-defined molecular structure, chemical inertness, and thermoresistance characteristics of aromatic polyimide (PI) material. Herein, for the first time a new porous carbon with controlled pore microstructure, large specific surface area and high micropore ratio was synthesized by pyrolyzing polyimide-linked COF (PI-COF-700). To investigate the influence of this pyrolyzed

porous COF, a three-component nanocomposite system based on polyaniline/poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) polystyrene sulfonate@PI-COF-700 (PANI/PEDOT: PSS@PI-COF-700) was developed which demonstrated an excellent supercapacitance and cycling performance. Though PANI is a well-known pseudocapacitive material, it suffers from poor cycling stability over time. Hence, blending PEDOT: PSS with PANI helps rectify this stability issue, improving its overall durability and performance in supercapacitor applications. Previously many PANI/PEDOT: PSS blends have been reported for a well-balanced and enhanced capacitance activity [33-35]. This research aims to understand the influence of PI-COF-700 in PANI/PEDOT: PSS blend, which may significantly improve the energy storage performance and its optimization for supercapacitors in the future.

Experimental methods

Materials

1,3,5-Tris(4-aminophenyl) benzene (TAPB), Pyromellitic dianhydride (PMDA), N-Methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP), Isoquinoline, methanol, acetone, ethanol, Tetrahydrofuran (THF), Sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4), Polyaniline (PANI), Poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) polystyrene sulfonate (PEDOT: PSS), graphite mesh, graphene oxide, multi-walled carbon nanotube were all obtained from Sigma-Aldrich. All solutions were prepared using type 1 ultrapure water ($>18 \text{ M}\Omega \text{ cm}$, Millipore).

Synthesis of Polyimide COF (PI-COF)

A 10mL Pyrex tube was charged with TAPB (1.054 g, 3mmol) and PMDA (0.9815 g, 3mmol) in a solution of 13.5 ml m-cresol/13.5 ml N-Methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP) in the presence of isoquinoline 0.18 ml. The Pyrex tube was degassed by freeze drying at 77K and flame sealed followed by heating at 200°C for 5 days. The resulting precipitate was washed with methanol (3x) and acetone (3x) and then recovered by centrifugation. The final material is purified by Soxhlet extraction in THF for 24h and then dried at 60°C under vacuum for 12h to acquire polyimide COF as a light-yellow powder with 89.1% (1.8139 g) isolated yield.

Preparation of PI-COF-700

The PI-COF was pelletized (13 mm diameter, 2 mm thickness and 314 mg per pellet), transferred into the alumina crucible and heating up to 700°C under N_2 atmosphere at $10^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ heating rate for 10 hours in a tubular furnace. Finally, the carbonized pellets (10 mm diameter, 2 mm thickness and 197.4 mg per pellet) were obtained as PI-COF-700. The PI-COF before and after carbonization are shown **Figure S1**.

Preparation of modified PANI/PEDOT: PSS@PI-COF-700 composites electrode and electrochemical measurement protocol

In first, following stock solutions were prepared; 4 mg of porous carbon, 4 mg of PI-COF, 4 mg PANI, 4 mg of PEDOT; PSS, 4 mg of graphite mesh, 4mg of graphene oxide where individually dispersed in 500 microliter ethanol and ultrasonicated for 5 minutes before coating on to the glassy-carbon electrode (GCE). From the stock solution 2 microliter of each active materials namely porous carbon, pure PANI, pure PEDOT: PSS, where separately coated onto the glassy-carbon electrode (GCE) and studied their individual CV responses. Following this, 4 microliters (1:1 ratio) of PANI/PEDOT: PSS blend, 6 microliters (1:1:1 ratio) of composites PANI/PEDOT: PSS@graphite mesh, PANI/PEDOT: PSS @graphene oxide and the optimal PANI/PEDOT: PSS@PI-COF-700 where drop casted on the GCE for the electrochemical analysis. The performance of individual porous carbon (PI-COF-700) and composite was evaluated using three-electrode system. Cyclic Voltammetry (CV) and Galvanostatic charge-discharge (GCD) were conducted on electrochemical potentiostat (VSP-300, BioLogic) at room temperature. The measurements were carried out in 0.5M H₂SO₄ electrolyte. GCE with active material was used as working electrode, a platinum wire as counter electrode and all the potentials were measured versus an Ag/AgCl reference electrode respectively. The area of glassy carbon electrode (GCE) was 0.07 cm². CV measurements for all the samples were measured at 50 mV s⁻¹. For the pure PI-COF-700 and PANI/PEDOT: PSS@PI-COF-700 samples, scan rate analysis was performed from 10-100 mV s⁻¹. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurements were conducted in a frequency range between 1Hz to 1 MHz in the 0.5M H₂SO₄ electrolyte solution using the amplitude of the sinusoidal voltage. GCD was performed at applied current density of 2 Ag⁻¹ for all the individual and modified composites. For the optimal systems (pure PI-COF-700 and PANI/PEDOT: PSS@PI-COF-700) continuous charge-discharge performances were studied at 20 Ag⁻¹.

Preparation of optimal PANI/PEDOT: PSS@PI-COF-700 composites electrode based Symmetric supercapacitor and its electrochemical measurement protocol

Two identical electrode of carbon paper (with 1×1 cm² working area, 0.15mm thickness) were used as cathode and anode for symmetric supercapacitor system fabrication. A slurry of optimal composite as active material, carbon black and PTFE in 8:1:1 ratio was obtained by mixing all together in NMP solvent. The mass loading on each electrode was ~3mg/cm². The electrochemical experiments were carried out in 0.5M H₂SO₄. CV measurements for the sample was measured at 50 mV s⁻¹, GCD was carried out at 0.2 and 0.3 Ag⁻¹, cycling stability was tested for 10,000 cycles at 30 Ag⁻¹. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS)

measurements were conducted before and after 10,000 cycles in a frequency range between 1Hz to 1 MHz.

Results and discussion

First, polyimide-linked COF (PI-COF) as a starting material was synthesized through the condensation reaction of 1,3,5-tris(4-aminophenyl) benzene (TAPB) and pyromellitic dianhydride (PMDA) under solvothermal conditions [36], then porous carbon (PI-COF-700) was prepared by pyrolysis of imide COF at 700 °C under nitrogen atmosphere. From the TGA results the material was found to be stable with minimal weight loss up to 700°C (refer **Figure S2**). The structural, morphological and compositional parameters of PI-COF and PI-COF-700 were investigated to explain their physicochemical properties. The successful imidization of PI-COF, followed by carbonization of PI-COF-700 (as shown in **Figure 1A**) were confirmed using XRD, FT-IR, and Raman spectroscopic techniques. **Figure S3** shows the typical XRD patterns of commercial TAPB and PMDA. As shown in **Figure 1B** (curve a), the XRD pattern of PI-COF possess intense diffraction peaks at $2\theta = 3.48^\circ$ (100), 6.88° (210), and 8.8° (200) represents the ordered structure of crystalline polyimide covalent organic framework, further the interlayer π - π stacking was confirmed from a broad peak 23° (001) [37]. Consequently, increasing the pyrolysis temperature to 700°C resulted in the appearance of two amorphous peaks, at $2\theta = 21.6^\circ$ corresponding to (002) reflecting the disordered nature of carbon and 43.5° (100), indicating the in-plane crystallinity of the graphite layer in PI-COF-700 (in **Figure 1B**, curve b) respectively [38]. The chemical structures of the starting materials (TAPB and PMDA), PI-COF and PI-COF-700 was confirmed by FTIR spectrum as shown in **Figure S4** and **Figure 1C** (a, b). The FT-IR spectrum of PI-COF shows essential signals confirming the presence of imide functional groups. The typical characteristic peaks, including C=O carbonyl group stretching vibration in 1773 (asymmetrical C=O) and 1716 cm^{-1} corresponds to the amide groups (symmetrical C=O) of polyimide rings, C-N stretching vibration at 1366 cm^{-1} , C=C aromatic stretching vibration around 1509 cm^{-1} , amine N-H stretching vibration around $3420\text{-}3490\text{ cm}^{-1}$ were obtained [39]. Further, **Figure 1C** (b curve) reveals the IR spectrum of the pyrolyzed amorphous PI-COF-700 system. An intense peak at 3351 cm^{-1} was attributed to -OH group stretching vibrations of the carbonization. The intense peak appearance may be due to the presence of isolated -OH molecules.

Figure 1 A. Schematic illustration of PI-COF and PI-COF-700 synthesis protocol, Physicochemical characterisations of PI-COF and Pyrolyzed PI-COF-700 by (B) XRD, (C) FTIR, (D) Raman spectroscopy

Another peak at 2928 cm^{-1} is related to aromatic C-H stretching, resulting from the breakdown of the polymer structure. The peaks in 1707 , 1677 and 1501 cm^{-1} correspond to C=O (asymmetrical and symmetrical) and C=C stretching, indicating the presence of graphitic units. In addition, a weak peak at 1366 cm^{-1} refers to C-N stretching, which may be a remnant from the PI-COF structure due to the low degree of carbonization [40]. The characteristic Raman spectrum of PI-COF in **Figure 1D** (curve a) before carbonization can be assigned to C-N stretching vibrations of the imide system ~ 1234 and 1369 cm^{-1} , C=C stretching vibrations at 1595 cm^{-1} and C=O stretching in the imide ring $\sim 1782\text{ cm}^{-1}$ [41]. After carbonization of PI-COF at $700\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, the graphitic nature of PI-COF-700 was identified from the Raman spectrum. The typical D and G bands of the graphitic structure are observed at 1320 cm^{-1} and 1580 cm^{-1} for the PI-COF-700, (**Figure 1D**, curve b) respectively. The D-band reflects disorders and defects in graphitic structures with sp^3 hybridized carbon atoms, while the G-band refers to the ordered graphitic layer with sp^2 hybridization caused by in-plane tangential stretching vibration [42, 43]. To make a comparative analysis for the newly graphitized porous carbon, we have depicted the Raman spectra of multi-walled carbon nanotube (MWCNT) and graphene oxide in **Figure S5** (a and b). We have also calculated the I_D/I_G values for all the graphitic samples (PI-COF-700, MWCNT, graphene oxide) to determine the degree of defects in the as-prepared porous carbon (PI-COF-700) material. The I_D/I_G intensity ratio values of PI-COF-700, MWCNT and graphene oxide were observed to be 1.35, 0.96 and 0.71 respectively, suggesting

the presence of plentiful defective structure in the pyrolyzed PI-COF-700 than MWCNT and graphene oxide.

Next, the defects and surface properties of PI-COF and the pyrolyzed PI-COF-700 samples are studied in detail by nitrogen adsorption/desorption measurement, Scanning electron microscope (SEM), Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). The porous structure of PI-COF and PI-COF-700 is determined by BET surface area measurements. The nitrogen adsorption/desorption isotherm plot of PI-COF and graphitized PI-COF-700 shows a typical Type-I isotherm (**Figure 2a, b**). The BET specific surface area of PI-COF was $335 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$, while the graphitized PI-COF-700 exhibited a significantly larger surface area of $1080 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$. The inset plots (**Figure 2a, b**) illustrate the pore size distribution of PI-COF before and after pyrolysis. The frequent pore size distribution around 2.2 nm, indicating mesoporous characteristics for the PI-COF. In contrast, PI-COF-700 exhibited a dominant pore size of 1 nm which is the characteristic of microporosity, with a smaller region around 2.4 nm, indicating of mesoporosity. This finding suggests that pyrolyzed PI-COF-700 features predominately uniform microporous structure, with minimal mesoporosity, which is likely associated to the structural defects. Thus, PI-COF-700 has a large surface area with more active sites and an increase in the proportion of micropores nature, which is necessary to enhance electron transport in electrochemical energy storage performance [44].

Figure 2. Nitrogen adsorption/desorption isotherm of (a) PI-COF and (b) N-porous COF, (insets of Figure 2a, b represents the corresponding pore size distribution plots using density function theory)

In addition, the morphological properties of the as-prepared PI-COF and PI-COF-700 were thoroughly investigated using SEM and TEM images. **Figure 3(a, b)** displays the SEM micrographs of PI-COF and PI-COF-700, and their matching energy dispersive x-ray spectrum was shown in **Figure S6**. The PI-COF had a consistent 2D structure and regular morphology with pores on the surface at higher

Figure 3. Scanning electron microscopy images, a) PI-COF, b) PI-COF-700, Transmission electron microscopy images of (c-d) PI-COF and (f-g) PI-COF-700, higher resolution transmission electron microscopy images (e, h) PI-COF and PI-COF-700.

magnification. Notably, the surface of PI-COF-700 was observed to have an irregular grain size morphology, indicating that the microporosity was developed after pyrolysis. The increase in

surface area was previously confirmed from the BET results. For better morphological features, the pristine PI-COF and PI-COF-700 were examined by TEM and HR-TEM (**Figure 3c-h**, respectively). The results further demonstrated that, the nanoparticles that make up PI-COF are approximately 35–40 nm in size and are tightly bound to each other (**Figure 3c, d**). The HR-TEM image (in **Figure 3e**), on the other hand, reveals the mesoporous nature of pristine PI-COF. Meanwhile, due to the mass loss during the pyrolysis process of PI-COF there was a marked structural shrinkage observed in **Figure 3f, g** (for PI-COF-700). The HR-TEM image of pyrolyzed PI-COF-700 in **Figure 3h** is noteworthy because it displays a wormlike network, which represents the amorphous porous carbon nature. This observation suggest that physical activation of PI-COF induces structural defects through the formation of uniform micropores [45]. These results are consistent with BET surface area and pore size measurements as well as Raman data. In addition, the High-angle annular dark-field and elemental mapping images shown in **Figure S7 (a-h)** of PI-COF and PI-COF-700 clearly revealed the uniform distribution of C, O, and N in the porous skeleton. Such heteroatoms present in the porous structure are suitable for improved electron transfer behaviour and electrochemical performances.

To confirm the above-mentioned elemental composition and chemical bonding states on the surface, the PI-COF and PI-COF-700 are further investigated by XPS. The chemical composition, chemical bonding and peak assignment are shown in **Table S1, S2, S3, S4** and **Figure 4(a-f)**. The PI-COF primarily consists of carbon (81.9 at%), oxygen (11.9 at%), and nitrogen (6.2 at%). As shown in **Figure 4(a-c)** PI-COF before carbonization indicates the existence of three major C species, three O and two N species. The C1s peak at 284.6 eV is attributed to C–C, 285.5 eV can be ascribed to C–O, C–N and 288.9 corresponds to the C=O carbonyl groups of the imide ring respectively. The O1s XPS spectra exhibit three peaks, centered at 532.3, 533.8 and 530.9 eV corresponding to the, C=O, C–O (aromatic group) and aliphatic C–O. The N1s XPS spectra (**Figure 4c**) show two peaks centered at 400.7 and 399.1 eV corresponding to the C–NH⁺ and C–N, N=C amide nitrogen groups respectively [46]. After pyrolysis, the carbon content increases to 93 at%, while the oxygen and nitrogen concentrations decrease to 3.4 at% and 3.6 at%, respectively. Despite this reduction, small amounts of oxygen and nitrogen remain in the porous carbon skeleton even after pyrolysis at 700°C, which is due to the initial high composition of these elements in the imide COF structure. In **Figure 4(d-f)**, the fitted peaks at 283.1, 284.6, 286.4 and 288.3 eV correspond to sp², sp³, C–O, C–N, C=O of C1s spectrum [47], while the O1s peaks are centered at 530.8, 529.2 and 532.3 eV corresponding to C=O, C–O (aliphatic), and C–O bonds of aromatics, respectively. The

pyridinic nitrogen, which is present at the edges of graphitic layers in aromatic networks, can be attributed to the N1s at 397 eV (C–N, N=C). The peak at 399 eV (N–C=O) corresponds to pyrrolic nitrogen or nitrogen atoms present in the imide group, and a peak at 400.5 eV (C–NH⁺) is associated with graphitic nitrogen. The shift from 399.1 to 397 eV of nitrogen group (C–N, N=C) before and after carbonization is due to the transformation of nitrogen group into more stable forms like pyridinic nitrogen or the aromatic nitrogen structure leading to the formation of a defective carbon network. This observation is consistent with the FT-IR analysis. As a result of this, more active sites are provided by nitrogen linkage in the porous carbon network, which may influence on the electrical and electrochemical properties of PI-COF-700 [48].

Figure 4. XPS energy level spectra of C1s, O1s, N1s of (a-c) PI-COF and (d-f) PI-COF-700

Furthermore, a composite was prepared by inducing PI-COF-700 in PANI/PEDOT: PSS system to better understand the influence of porous carbon in the conducting polymer network. The PANI/PEDOT: PSS matrix was selected as an additive material for compositing with PI-COF-700 because, PEDOT has been shown to reduce the electron hopping distance, thereby

enhancing electrical conductivity when PANI is incorporated into the PEDOT: PSS system [35]. PANI is well-known for its redox active nature and high pseudocapacitance response, while PEDOT: PSS is not as redox active as PANI. Moreover, our observations as depicted in **Figure S8** indicates that, the PANI/PEDOT: PSS@PI-COF-700-based three-component system exhibited superior electron transfer trend when compared to PANI@PI-COF-700 (78.12 Fg^{-1}) and PEDOT: PSS@PI-COF-700 (16.18 Fg^{-1}) respectively. So, the utilization of PEDOT; PSS in the PANI@PI-COF-700 matrix synergically improved electrochemical performance and structural integrity.

Also, lowest bandgap value of 3.43eV was observed for PANI/PEDOT: PSS@PI-COF-700 which is evident (refer **Figure S9** and **Table S5**) from the UV-Vis analysis. **Figure 5A** represents the schematic illustration and possible interaction of PANI/PEDOT: PSS with PI-COF-700. Furthermore, the electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) was performed to study the ion transport behaviour and resistance characteristics observed at the electrode, electrolyte and their interface. The experiment was performed in a three-electrode system using, $0.5\text{M H}_2\text{SO}_4$ electrolyte medium, in the frequency range from 1Hz to 1MHz . The Nyquist plot of PI-COF-700 (**Figure 5B** inset plot), PANI/PEDOT: PSS blend and PANI/PEDOT: PSS@PI-COF-700 are presented in **Figure 5B**, showing a feeble semi-circle in the high frequency region and an inclined straight-line response in the low-frequency region, relating to the mechanism of ion diffusion into the active material deposited on the electrode. The obtained EIS response for all the samples were curve fitted using the Randles circuit model $R_s [C_{dl} (R_{ct} W_1)]$, where R_s is the equivalent series resistance (ESR-non Faradic), C_{dl} is double layer capacitance, R_{ct} is the charge transfer resistance (Faradic) and W_1 is Warburg impedance (corresponding to the straight line in the low frequency region) respectively. The ESR and R_{ct} values were calculated to be 5.4 and 6Ω for PI-COF-700, 4.8 and 6.9Ω for PANI/PEDOT: PSS blend, finally 4.9 and 3.3Ω for PI-COF-700 induced PANI/PEDOT: PSS composite system respectively. The composite's enhanced electrochemical impedance was observed from the low charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) of 3.3Ω value, which was achieved by the nitrogen-rich porous carbon doping into PANI/PEDOT: PSS matrix that improved wettability while facilitating ion transport [49]. This observation is also consistent with the lowest bandgap value obtained for the PANI/PEDOT: PSS@PI-COF-700 composite from the UV-Vis analysis as depicted in **Figure S9** and **Table S5**. Additionally, the chemical interaction mechanism can be confirmed with the broad OH shift to 3420 cm^{-1} and C=C stretching shift to 1560 and 1477 cm^{-1} respectively in the PANI/PEDOT: PSS@PI-COF-700 nanocomposite, possibly due to the

hydrogen bonding as well as π - π interaction between polymer matrix and the carbonized COF as depicted in **Figure S10**. These strong interactions may be beneficial for the improved EIS performance [50].

Meanwhile, the contribution of surface and ion-diffusion in the electrochemical performance of PI-COF-700 and PANI-PEDOT: PSS@PI-COF-700 has been investigated by Dunn's method. The combinatory effect of two different mechanism i) surface controlled (capacitive) and ii) diffusion controlled (like faradaic) and their contribution percentage in the porous composite electrode materials were analysed using the following equation [51].

$$i(V) = k_1v + k_2v^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

Here, we can quantitatively analyse the capacitive (k_1) and diffusion-controlled (k_2) contributions derived from the current response at a fixed potential. **Figure 5(C-E)** illustrates the CV response and bar chart of PI-COF-700 and its composite with PANI-PEDOT: PSS demonstrating the quantitative capacitive and diffusion contributions.

Figure 5. A) Schematic illustration with possible interaction of PANI/PEDOT: PSS@PI-COF-700, B) Nyquist plot of PI-COF-700 (inset plot), PANI/PEDOT: PSS and PANI/PEDOT:PSS@PI-COF-700, C) & D) CV response of PI-COF-700, PANI/PEDOT:PSS@PI-COF-700 at 50mV s^{-1} and E) Bar chart indicating the capacitive and diffusion contribution mechanism.

COF-700 and PANI/PEDOT: PSS@PI-COF-700 at a scan rate of 50 mV s^{-1} in $0.5\text{M H}_2\text{SO}_4$ electrolyte medium, at potential window range from -0.2 V to $+0.8\text{ V}$ (vs Ag/AgCl). The green shaded area in the CV graphs highlights the capacitive contribution in both the pure PI-COF-700 and the optimal composite systems. Meanwhile, the bar chart in **Figure 5E**, demonstrated that 94% of the stored charges in PI-COF-700 is attributed to surface contributions. However, upon compositing PI-COF-700 with PANI-PEDOT: PSS, the charge storage mechanism shifts to being predominantly diffusion-controlled (85%), since the surface redox reactions are superior in the composite system. The synergistic effect of capacitive and diffusive contributions has significantly enhanced the overall pseudocapacitance property of the composite electrode material. Notably, the type of electrolyte (acid, basic, neutral) employed in each system and its capability to diffuse into the electrode material [52] generally play a crucial role in electrochemical energy storage performance. By trial-and-error method only we have employed H_2SO_4 electrolyte in our system (as in **Figure S12b**). Particularly, in acidic electrolyte condition, the reaction at the electrode-electrolyte interface like charge/discharge process tends to be faster due to the availability of plenty of protons (H^+ ions). This leads to improved charge storage mechanism and faster cycling, which is desirable in applications where quick energy delivery is important.

Furthermore, the energy storage performance of PI-COF-700 in PANI-PEDOT: PSS composite was evaluated by three- electrode system, where $0.5\text{M H}_2\text{SO}_4$ solution medium was utilized at 50mV s^{-1} scan rate, in an applied voltage range from -0.2 V to $+0.8\text{ V}$. At first, the CV response of PI-COF-700, polymer blends and control sample were analysed. In general, the Faradaic system exhibits a large electron-transfer reaction with a distinct peak current signal, the modified electrode made of capacitor-like material generally displays a large non-Faradic current signal with a box shape current feature (without any peak current response) [53]. **Figure 6a, b** represents the typical CV response of PI-COF-700, pure PEDOT: PSS, pure PANI, PANI-PEDOT: PSS blend, PANI/PEDOT: PSS@PI-COF-700 composite. Being a carbonaceous material, PI-COF-700 (in **Figure 6ai**) possess an excellent double-layer capacitance response (EDLC) which can be clearly seen from its CV graph trend. The scan

rate effect of PI-COF-700 is depicted in **Figure S11(a)**. Moreover, the CV curve of PEDOT: PSS has shown a large capacitive background current area with box-like appearance suggesting EDLC response with feeble redox peak signal around 0.45 V in **Figure 6a(ii)**, respectively. The specific redox signal observed for pure polyaniline (PANI) (in **Figure 6b(i)**) is linked to proton-transfer-electron-transfer responses, indicating PANI's pseudocapacitance nature [54]. Unlike other polymers, which primarily store charge on their surface, PANI stores charge through redox reactions (Faradaic response) involving oxidation shifts, due to utilization of its entire volume [55]. A high specific current trend was noticed for PANI/PEDOT: PSS blend than the pure PANI electrode suggesting that PANI/PEDOT: PSS polymer blend could have improved specific capacitance and electrochemical performances in **Figure 6b(ii)**. Furthermore, the CV curve of the PI-COF-700 modified PANI/PEDOT: PSS composite system (as shown in **Figure 6b(iii)**) exhibits a feeble box shape and a clearly improved prominent redox peak than the pure PANI and PANI/PEDOT: PSS responses. The subsequent feeble peak at 0.5 V indicated that PEDOT: PSS does, in fact, enhanced the energy storage capacity, by the appearance of fine-tuned secondary redox peak signal behaviour in the composite material. However, majority of redox response is from PANI than PEDOT: PSS in PI-COF-700 modified PANI/PEDOT: PSS system. Overall, the capacitive behaviour is due to the combined effects of EDLC and pseudocapacitance characteristics in the resultant composite material.

Figure 6. CV curve of a) (i-ii) PI-COF-700, PEDOT:PSS, b) (i-iii) PANI, PANI-PEDOT:PSS blend, PANI-PEDOT:PSS@PI-COF-700 in 0.5M H₂SO₄ solution at scan rate 50 mV s⁻¹, Galvanostatic charge/discharge response of c) (i-ii) PI-COF-700, PEDOT:PSS, d) (i-iii) PANI, PANI-PEDOT:PSS, PANI-PEDOT:PSS@PI-COF-700 in 0.5M H₂SO₄ solution at an applied current density of 2 Ag⁻¹, e) The continuous charge-discharge response of PANI-PEDOT:PSS@PI-COF-700 at an applied current density of 20 Ag⁻¹ for 1000 cycles and f) Ragone plot

of PANI-PEDOT:PSS@PI-COF-700 composite's supercapacitance performance compared with different porous carbon- based literature reports.

As mentioned earlier from **Figure S8(a)**, the best charge transfer signal was observed for PANI/PEDOT: PSS@PI-COF-700 with large background current than individual PI-COF-700 induced PANI and PEDOT: PSS systems. This enhanced capacitance performance of the optimal composite is attributed to the increased surface area, higher micropore ratio, and the presence of N-atoms in the porous carbon which enhance the electron transfer reaction, within the PANI/PEDOT: PSS matrix, predominantly contributing to the pseudocapacitance activity. Further the influence of scan rate effect on the optimal PANI/PEDOT: PSS@PI-COF-700 were shown in **Figure S12**. The pseudo-capacitance behaviour ($v= 10-100\text{mV s}^{-1}$) was consistent, implying their excellent rate capability. Meanwhile, two unique redox peaks were seen across all scan rates, indicating the interconversion of the emeraldine and leucoemeraldine states of PANI [56] and the combinatory effect of PEDOT: PSS. For comparison purpose, the same concentration of PANI/PEDOT: PSS was composited with commercial graphite mesh and graphene oxide in replacement of the “as-prepared” PI-COF-700 and then subjected to CV analysis (as shown in **Figure S13**). The comparative result indicated that the PI-COF-700 doped composite system outperformed the other commercial carbon-based composite systems in terms of electrochemical performance.

Furthermore, to study the charge storage performance the PI-COF-700 and composite system, the galvanostatic charge-discharge analysis was performed in 0.5M H₂SO₄ at an applied current density of 2 Ag⁻¹. **Figure 6c (i-ii)** exhibits the charge-discharge curve of pure systems PI-COF-700 and PEDOT: PSS systems, whereas **Figure 6d (i-iii)** represents the charge-discharge response of pure PANI, PANI/PEDOT: PSS blend and PANI/PEDOT: PSS@PI-COF-700 composite. As can be seen in **Figure 6c (i and ii plot)**, the PI-COF-700 and PEDOT: PSS showed feeble capacitance response when compared to PANI and other modified electrode materials (in **Figure 6d**). Furthermore, PI-COF-700 loaded composite system in **Figure 6d (iii)** exhibited about one-third times improved charge-discharge response than PANI/PEDOT: PSS blend respectively. Following this, to confirm the individual capacitance value of all the samples, the specific capacitance (C_s) was calculated using the following standard formula [57].

$$C_s = \frac{I \times \Delta t}{m \times \Delta V} \text{ F g}^{-1}$$

Where the $I(A)$, Δt (s), $m(g)$, ΔV (V) represents the discharge current, discharge time, mass of active material coated on to the electrode (g) and change in potential window, respectively. Following are the summary of values obtained: 14 Fg^{-1} for PEDOT: PSS, 19.4 Fg^{-1} for PI-COF-700, 600 Fg^{-1} for PANI, 515.62 Fg^{-1} for PANI/PEDOT: PSS blend and $729.17 \text{ Fg}^{-1} (\pm 7)$ for PANI/PEDOT: PSS@PI-COF-700 at an applied current density of 2 Ag^{-1} respectively. There is $\sim 0.2 \text{ V}$ of voltage drop noticed in the intersection point of the charge-discharge plot for all the PANI modified electrodes (in **Figure 6d**) indicating the existence of internal resistance and slow diffusion rate [58]. Possibly, the increased wettability [59], hydrogen bonding and π - π stacking between the porous carbon and PANI/PEDOT: PSS all together synergistically contributed to the improved electrochemical performance of the optimal composite system.

Regarding the overall charge storage performance: PEDOT: PSS contributes relatively less capacitance activity in PANI/PEDOT: blend due to their less redox active sites. It is noteworthy, as the CV response of PANI@PI-COF-700 depicted in **Figure S8** is comparatively lower than PANI/PEDOT: PSS blend. Hence PEDOT: PSS played a crucial role in improving the stability of the composite, whereas PANI contributed significantly to the pseudocapacitance characteristics. In the meantime, the addition of PI-COF-700 greatly enhanced the capacitance performance of the composite system respectively. The charge-discharge response in **Figure 6e** was steady and unaltered over an extended period of time up to 1000 cycles at an applied current density of 20 Ag^{-1} and the capacitance retention was observed to be $\sim 92.2\%$. Adding on to this, 90% of its initial capacitance was retained for the pure PI-COF-700 at an applied current density of 20 Ag^{-1} after 1000 cycles in **Figure S11(b)**. Furthermore, the PI-COF-700 composite electrode (**Figure S14**) was used to test the influence of applied current by varying the bias current as 100 and 200 μA (2 and 20 Ag^{-1}). The findings indicate a low pseudo-capacitance behaviour at high bias current and a noticeable reversal observation at low bias current. Hence 100 μA is the optimal applied bias current suitable for the composite system in this work. Notably, the specific capacitance value achieved in this work for the PI-COF-700-induced PANI/PEDOT: PSS system is superior and closely comparable to the values reported for previously studied porous carbons derived from organic frameworks and other porous carbon-based composite. From the illustration of Ragone plot (**Figure 6f**): 455 Fg^{-1} for PANI/N-doped porous carbon (at 1 Ag^{-1}) [60], 287 Fg^{-1} for COF based microporous carbon-(TAPT DHTA-COF_{0.1}@ polycyclotriphosphazene-co-4,4'sulfonyldiphenol) (at 1 Ag^{-1}) [24], 196 Fg^{-1} for copper metal organic framework (MOF) derived PC (at 0.5 Ag^{-1}) [61], 199.9 Fg^{-1}

for MOF derived PC/chitosan (at 0.05 Ag^{-1}) [62], 525 Fg^{-1} for COF based porous carbon (N-PC)/manganese dioxide (MnO_2) (at 1 Ag^{-1}) [63], 278 Fg^{-1} for Carbon nanotube-Imide COF composite (at 0.5 Ag^{-1}) [64], 129.2 Fg^{-1} for COF/Carbon foam composite (at 0.5 Ag^{-1}) [65], 181 Fg^{-1} for lignin derived activated carbon/PEDOT (at 1 Ag^{-1}) [66], 223 Fg^{-1} for Polyvinyl alcohol derived PC/ reduced graphene oxide (rGO) (at 1 Ag^{-1}) [67], 240 Fg^{-1} for Manganese doped nickel and cobalt hydroxide nanosheet-PANI derived porous carbon (at 1 Ag^{-1}) [68], 630 Fg^{-1} for N-rGO/PQ (9,10-phenanthrenequinone) composite (at 5 Ag^{-1}) [69] and, 383 Fg^{-1} for COF-derived PC-tin oxide (SnO_2) composite (at 2 Ag^{-1}) [70] respectively. Furthermore, the above comparative literature reports on various test conditions and specific capacitance values have been summarized in **Table S6** for clarity purpose.

Figure 7. Performance of fabricated optimal PANI-PEDOT:PSS@PI-COF-700 composite electrodes as symmetric supercapacitor system: CV curve of a) PANI-PEDOT:PSS@PI-COF-700 in $0.5 \text{ M H}_2\text{SO}_4$ solution at scan rate 50 mV s^{-1} , Galvanostatic charge/discharge response of b) PANI-PEDOT:PSS@PI-COF-700 in $0.5 \text{ M H}_2\text{SO}_4$ solution at an applied current density of 0.2 (black) and 0.3 (red) Ag^{-1} , c) The continuous charge-discharge response of PANI-PEDOT:PSS@PI-COF-700 at an applied current density of 30 Ag^{-1} for 10,000 cycles and d) Nyquist plot of PANI-PEDOT:PSS@PI-COF-700 composite before (blue) and after (pink) 10,000 cycles (inset showing first and last 30 cycles)

Additionally, electrochemical performance of the optimal PANI/PEDOT: PSS@PI-COF-700 composite as symmetric supercapacitor (two-electrode) was evaluated using CV, GCD and EIS analysis. **Figure 7a** shows the CV profile of symmetric supercapacitor at a sweep rate of 50mV/s, the assembly is stable with obvious EDLC and pseudocapacitive response in 0.5M H₂SO₄ aqueous electrolyte. **Figure 7b** reveals the GCD profile of the two-electrode system at two different current densities of 0.2 and 0.3 Ag⁻¹, respectively. A maximum C_s of 181.82 Fg⁻¹ (± 2) at 0.2 Ag⁻¹ was obtained with the cell voltage of 1V. Further, when the current density was increased to 0.3 Ag⁻¹, the C_s was decreased to 152.72 Fg⁻¹. Followingly, long-term electrochemical stability of the fabricated symmetric supercapacitor was investigated by continuous cycling for 10,000 cycles with high charging current of 100 mA (30 Ag⁻¹) for 1V. **Figure 7c** shows the capacitance retention of the “as-prepared” symmetric supercapacitor as a function of cycling number. From the graph, it is clear that more than 89.81% of the capacitance was retained and a coulombic efficiency was calculated about ~90.9% after 10,000 charge-discharge cycle, which confirms an excellent electrochemical stability of the symmetrical supercapacitor system. As a representation, first and last 30 continuous charge-discharge profiles were depicted in **Figure 7c** (inset). Furthermore, **Figure 7d** reveals the Nyquist plot of the “as-prepared” symmetric electrodes before and after 10,000 cycles, which exhibit R_s ~2.05 (before cycling), 2.06 Ω (after cycling) and R_{ct} 4.3 (before cycling), 4.55 Ω (after cycling), respectively. The results suggested that the active components (nitrogen-rich porous carbon doping into the PANI/PEDOT: PSS with additives) in the electrode remains stable even after prolonged cycling in acidic conditions and excellent electrical contact [71]. Additionally, from the FTIR results, there is strong hydrogen bonding interaction within the composite material which facilitated superior electrochemical activity (please refer **Figure S10**). We further tested the same electrode for CV and EIS techniques in a 5 mM ferricyanide redox couple within a 0.5M KCl medium, a benchmarking system that offers insights into the electrical and electrochemical properties of solid electrode materials through their redox activity [72]. As shown in **Figure S15 and Table S7**, no significant change in the R_{ct} value was observed before and after the long cycling experiment, likely due to pseudocapacitive-assisted surface reactions at the electrode/electrolyte interface.

Conclusion

In summary, a novel porous carbon material was developed using a periodically ordered porous PI-COF precursor, resulted in an appreciable yield of defective carbon (PI-COF-700). The successful formation of PI-COF and subsequent carbonization of PI-COF-700 are confirmed

through various techniques. Chemical structural transformation of key functional groups associated with the imide linkage were confirmed by FTIR. The carbonized PI-COF-700 exhibited more disordered carbon network, as evidenced by a higher I_D/I_G ratio in the Raman spectra which was also consistent with the BET results. Meanwhile, the frequent pore size distribution from BET analysis suggested a transition from mesoporous to microporous structures and a significant increase in the specific surface area to $1080 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ after pyrolysis of PI-COF. The uniform distribution of a worm-like network confirmed that, the carbonization process successfully induced micropore formation. XPS indicated the presence of nitrogen atoms in the PI-COF-700, which probably contributed to the formation of defects in the carbon structure. When PI-COF-700 is incorporated into a PANI/PEDOT: PSS polymer system, the composite demonstrated an improved impedance response with a reduced resistance value of 3.3Ω , thereby enhancing the ion transport, which is crucial for high-performance electrical applications. Additionally, the PANI/PEDOT: PSS@PI-COF-700 composite system exhibited much better pseudocapacitance behaviour, with an excellent specific capacitance of 729.17 Fg^{-1} at 2 Ag^{-1} respectively. The composite also showed a good cycling stability at 20 Ag^{-1} , with 92.2% capacitance retention after 1000 charge-discharge cycles. Additionally, the optimal composite PANI/PEDOT: PSS@PI-COF-700 based symmetric-electrode system demonstrated a high specific capacitance of 181.82 Fg^{-1} at 0.2 Ag^{-1} , and a capacitance retention of 89.81% was maintained after 10,000 cycles. The outstanding electrical contact and low resistance loss, even after prolonged cycling of the symmetric supercapacitor was confirmed from EIS measurements. Probably the nitrogen linkage in the microporous PI-COF-700 network generated defects/active sites that may have influenced on the electrical and electrochemical properties of the modified composite system. This study effectively demonstrates that the combination of high surface area, nitrogen doping, and its structural interaction in composite system can lead to enhanced electrochemical energy storage capabilities. This method of pyrolyzing PI-COF represents an effective approach for the controlled preparation of porous carbon materials with tailored surface property. In an acidic environment, other carbon materials may corrode or degrade over prolonged cycling. In contrast, porous carbon derived from polyimide COF offers a stable chemical structure, tolerate high temperatures and can withstand harsh chemical conditions. It is expected that PI-COF-derived porous carbon-based composite system investigated in this work can be used to develop high-performance energy storage devices in future.

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge at

Additional data: Experimental methods (Materials); Pyrolysis photograph; TGA and DSC curve of PI-COF; XRD pattern of TAPB and PMDA; FTIR Spectrum of TAPB and PMDA; Raman Spectrum of MWCNT and Graphene oxide; Energy dispersive x-ray spectrum of PI-COF and PI-COF-700; HAADF image and elemental mapping images of PI-COF and PI-COF-700; Tables of XPS analysis and Chemical composition of PI-COF and PI-COF-700; CV Curve of PI-COF-700 at different composition; UV-Vis spectra of PI-COF-700 at different composition; Table bandgap values of PI-COF-700 at different composition from UV-Vis analysis; FTIR Spectrum of PANI/PEDOT: PSS@ PI-COF-700; Scan rate effect of PI-COF-700 and long term cycling stability of PI-COF-700; Scan rate effect of PANI/PEDOT: PSS@PI-COF-700; CV response of PANI/PEDOT: PSS@PI-COF-700 in different electrolyte medium; CV response of different graphitic system-based PANI/PEDOT: PSS composites; GCD response of PANI/PEDOT: PSS@PI-COF-700 at different applied current densities; Comparative literature reports as table; CV and EIS 0.5M KCl and 5 mM of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$ solution medium; EIS table (PDF)

Declaration of Competing Interest

None

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